

Supplementary materials for “What happens when the lights are left on? Transcriptomic and phenotypic habituation to light pollution”

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Table S1: Generalized linear mixed-effect model to test whether behavioral responses of naïve birds to ALAN (count of active minutes per night) depend on time of year animals were exposed (stage). There was no significant effect of sex, so it was dropped from the final model. Fixed effects include day (integer) and the interaction of ALAN (factor) and stage (factor), with individual as a random effect to account for repeated measures and a Poisson distribution.

Predictor	IRR ¹	SE	CI(95%)	p
Day	1.00	0.002	1.00, 1.00	0.433
ALAN	2.31	0.919	1.06, 5.04	0.035
ALAN * stage				
0 * 3	0.87	0.145	0.63, 1.21	0.407
1 * 3	1.27	0.539	0.55, 2.92	0.579

¹ IRR = Incidence Rate Ratio

Table S2: Linear mixed-effect models to test whether oxidative responses of naïve birds to ALAN depend on duration of captivity or time of year animals were exposed. Fixed effects include sex (factor), ALAN treatment group (factor) and day (integer), with individual bird as a random effect to account for repeated measures. There was no significant interaction of ALAN and day, so the interactive term was dropped from the final model. Results of models using a combined stress index as well as individual biomarkers (oxy absorbance and dROMs).

Predictor	Stress Index				Oxy Absorbance				dROMs			
	β	SE	CI (95%)	p	β	SE	CI (95%)	p	β	SE	CI (95%)	p
Sex	0.79	0.342	0.07, 1.5	0.033	-33	19.6	-73, 8.1	0.110	0.51	0.815	-1.2, 2.2	0.539
Day	-0.02	0.017	-0.06, 0.01	0.166	0.19	0.635	-1.1, 1.5	0.768	-0.06	0.039	-0.14, 0.02	0.134
ALAN	-0.09	0.288	-0.67, 0.48	0.748	-2.0	10.7	-24, 19	0.850	-0.25	0.657	-1.6, 1.1	0.704

Table S3. Gene annotation analysis of down- and upregulated genes for 1) naïve ALAN exposure compared to acclimation period (pre-ALAN); 2) Recovery 11 weeks post-exposure compared to during naïve exposures, and 3) Secondary re-exposure compared to naïve exposure. Gene annotation analysis conducted in Metascape (53). Only top 20 results are shown, and all *q*-values of less than 0.05 are bolded. Full output available on GitHub (<https://github.com/valaasam>)

	Direction	Category	Name	# of Genes	<i>p</i>	<i>q</i>
Naïve Exposure	Down-regulated	Reactome Gene Sets	Cellular response to stress	15	< 0.001	< 0.001
			Neddylation	8	< 0.001	0.004
			Golgi Associated Vesicle Biogenesis	4	< 0.001	0.044
			Oxygen-dependent proline hydroxylation of Hypoxia-inducible Factor Alpha	4	< 0.001	0.074
			GO Biological Processes	Hemopoiesis	11	< 0.001
		Response to peptide	8	< 0.001	0.089	
		Cellular response to decreased oxygen levels	5	< 0.001	0.089	
Recovery	Down-regulated	KEGG Pathway	Platelet activation	19	< 0.001	< 0.001
			Focal adhesion	19	< 0.001	< 0.001
			Leukocyte transendothelial migration	11	< 0.001	< 0.001
			Thyroid hormone signaling	11	< 0.001	< 0.001
		WikiPathways	VEGFA-VEGFR2 signaling	22	< 0.001	< 0.001
			Myometrial relaxation and contraction	11	< 0.001	< 0.001
		Canonical Pathways	PID FAK	9	< 0.001	< 0.001
		Reactome Gene Sets	Muscle contraction	14	< 0.001	< 0.001
		GO Biological Processes	Response to wounding	29	< 0.001	< 0.001
			Actin cytoskeleton organization	28	< 0.001	< 0.001
			Positive regulation of cell migration	24	< 0.001	< 0.001
			Regulation of vesicle-mediated transport	23	< 0.001	< 0.001
			Cellular response to nitrogen compound	23	< 0.001	< 0.001
			Regulation of kinase activity	23	< 0.001	< 0.001
			Circulatory system process	21	< 0.001	< 0.001
			Cellular response to organic cyclic compound	19	< 0.001	< 0.001
			Regulation of cell-substrate junction organization	10	< 0.001	< 0.001
			Actomyosin structure organization	10	< 0.001	< 0.001
			Release of sequestered calcium ion into cytosol	8	< 0.001	< 0.001
			Cell-substrate junction assembly	7	< 0.001	< 0.001
Up-regulated	WikiPathways		Translation factors	6	< 0.001	< 0.001
		Reactome Gene Sets	Asparagine N-linked glycosylation	9	< 0.001	0.023
	GO Biological Processes	Hypusine synthesis from eIF5A-lysine	3	< 0.001	< 0.001	
		Translation	33	< 0.001	< 0.001	
		Endomembrane system organization	17	< 0.001	< 0.001	
		Protein catabolic process	16	< 0.001	0.004	
		Ribosome biogenesis	13	< 0.001	< 0.001	
		Regulation of cellular amide metabolic process	12	< 0.001	0.033	
		Positive regulation of organelle organization	11	< 0.001	0.058	
		Aerobic electron transport chain	10	< 0.001	< 0.001	
		Cellular component disassembly	10	< 0.001	0.006	

			Response to oxidative stress	9	< 0.001	0.074
			Mitochondrial gene expression	8	< 0.001	0.001
			Regulation of proteolysis involved in protein catabolic process	8	< 0.001	0.017
			Protein localization to organelle	7	< 0.001	0.001
			Vacuole organization	7	< 0.001	0.022
			Protein folding	7	< 0.001	0.068
			Regulation of ubiquitin protein ligase activity	4	< 0.001	0.003
			tRNA threonylcarbamoyladenine metabolic process	3	< 0.001	0.033
		CORUM	Parvulin-associated pre-rRNP complex	3	< 0.001	0.009
Re-exposure	Down-regulated	KEGG Pathway	Regulation of actin cytoskeleton	21	< 0.001	< 0.001
			Platelet activation	17	< 0.001	< 0.001
			Leukocyte transendothelial migration	14	< 0.001	< 0.001
			Oxytocin signaling pathway	14	< 0.001	< 0.001
		WikiPathways	VEGFA-VEGFR2 signaling pathway	22	< 0.001	< 0.001
			Myometrial relaxation and contraction pathways	16	< 0.001	< 0.001
		Reactome Gene Sets	Hemostasis	35	< 0.001	< 0.001
			GPCR downstream signaling	25	< 0.001	< 0.001
			Cell-Cell communication	13	< 0.001	< 0.001
			Smooth Muscle Contraction	8	< 0.001	< 0.001
		GO Biological Processes	Actin filament-based process	35	< 0.001	< 0.001
			Regulation of body fluid levels	24	< 0.001	< 0.001
			Regulation of vesicle-mediated transport	24	< 0.001	< 0.001
			Positive regulation of cell migration	24	< 0.001	< 0.001
			Cell morphogenesis	23	< 0.001	< 0.001
			Regulation of anatomical structure size	21	< 0.001	< 0.001
			Regulation of GTPase activity	21	< 0.001	< 0.001
			Regulation of small GTPase mediated signal transduction	19	< 0.001	< 0.001
			Regulation of cell morphogenesis	17	< 0.001	< 0.001
Small GTPase mediated signal transduction	15		< 0.001	< 0.001		
Up-regulated	Canonical Pathways	PID Telomerase Pathway	5	< 0.001	0.012	
	GO Biological Processes	Immune system development	15	< 0.001	0.003	
		Histone modification	11	< 0.001	0.003	
		Neural tube closure	6	< 0.001	0.006	
		Chaperone cofactor-dependent protein Refolding	4	< 0.001	0.012	
		Negative regulation of macroautophagy	4	< 0.001	0.016	
		Nucleocytoplasmic transport	7	< 0.001	0.046	
		Heterochromatin formation	4	< 0.001	0.052	
		Protein autophosphorylation	6	< 0.001	0.071	
		Protein hydroxylation	3	< 0.001	0.091	
		Nucleus localization	3	< 0.001	0.091	
		Regulation of cell cycle process	11	< 0.001	0.100	
		Regulation of dephosphorylation	5	< 0.001	0.100	

Figure S1. Telomere lengths did not differ between ALAN and control groups at either timepoint (A). Males consistently had shorter telomeres than females across timepoints (B). Individual changes in telomere length over time were all positive, indicating a shortening of telomeres over time, but there was no difference in degree of attrition between groups (C).